

Irresolute β -topological Algebra

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce a generalization of topological R -module using β -open sets called irresolute β -topological algebra (group, ring and module). We show that the center of an irresolute β -hausdorff ring is β -closed and if N is Q -submodule of an irresolute β -topological R -module M , then $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is also $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ -submodule where Q, N are subsets of R, M respectively. Several other properties of them are investigated.

Keywords: β -open set, commutative ring, stable set, irresolute β -topological R -Module.

1. Preliminaries

In [1] Monsef et al defined β -open sets in a topological space. The class of β -open sets is contained in the classes of semi-open and pre-open sets. Many mathematicians investigated and studied the basic results and properties by replacing open sets with β -open sets. We generalize topological algebra into new concepts and find their properties in new setting. A subset A of a topological space X is said to be β -open set if $A \subseteq Cl(Int(Cl(A)))$. The intersection of all β -closed sets $A \subseteq X$ is called β -closure of A and denoted by $\beta Cl(A)$. It is well known that A is β -closed in X if and only if $\beta Cl(A) = A$. A point $x \in \beta Cl(A)$ if and only if $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ for each β -open set U in X containing x .

In [2], Mohammed Salih, defined an irresolute topological rings by using semi-open set and gave several properties about it. In [3] Billawria and Sharma, defined and studies β -topological rings.

Throughout this paper, the closure and the interior of A will be denoted by $Cl(A)$ and $Int(A)$, respectively. We use abbreviation $I\beta TG$ ($I\beta TR$, $I\beta TM$) to denote the irresolute β -topological group (the irresolute β -topological ring, the irresolute β -topological module). A map $f: X \rightarrow Y$ from a topological space X into a topological space Y is said to be continuous (β -continuous) if the inverse image of any open set of Y is open set (β -open set) in X . Furthermore, f is said to be irresolute β -continuous if the inverse image of any β -open set is β -open.

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Lemma 1.1. Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a mapping from a topological space into a topological space Y . Then f is an irresolute β -continuous if and only if $f(\beta Cl(A)) \subseteq \beta Cl(f(A))$ for all $A \subseteq X$.

Remark 1.2. Since every open set is β -open, every continuous map is β -continuous and every irresolute β -continuous map is β -continuous.

Let M be an R -module and $Q \subseteq R$. A subset S of M is called Q -stable if $Q.S \subseteq S$.

Our aim of this paper is to study some properties of a new type of topological algebra by using β -open sets. We will deal with different type of topological algebra. We will start with the following definition.

2. Irresolute β -topological groups

In this section, we define and study irresolute β -topological groups ($I\beta TG$) with some examples.

Definition 2.1. Let $(G, +)$ be a group. A topology on G is an irresolute β -topological group if the following conditions hold:

1. the mapping $f: G \times G \rightarrow G, f(x, y) = x + y$ is irresolute β -continuous.
2. the mapping $g: G \rightarrow G, g(x) = -x$ is irresolute β -continuous.

Example 2.2. Let \mathbb{R} be the group of real numbers, \mathbb{Q} and Irr be the set of rational and irrational numbers respectively and $\tau = \{\emptyset, Irr, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}\}$ be the topology on \mathbb{R} . Then (\mathbb{R}, τ) is $I\beta TG$.

From Remark 1.2, we deduce that every $I\beta TG$ is β -topological group and every topological group is β -topological group. However their converse are not true.

Example 2.3. The topological space (\mathbb{R}, τ) in [3, Example 3.8] is a β -topological group which is not a topological group nor an $I\beta TG$ because if we take the β -open set $\{\sqrt{2}\}$, there exist β -open sets $\{\sqrt{2}\}$ and $\{0, \sqrt{3}\}$ contain $\sqrt{2}$ and 0 respectively but their sum does not lie in $\{\sqrt{2}\}$.

Theorem 2.4. If G is an $I\beta TG$, then

1. The mapping $f: G \rightarrow G, f(x) = -x$ is an irresolute β -homeomorphism.
2. For every element $r \in G$, the mappings $R_r: G \rightarrow G, R_r(x) = x + r, L_r: G \rightarrow G, L_r(x) = r + x$ are irresolute β -homeomorphisms.

PROOF. It is clear that f, L_r and R_r are bijective functions. The rest follows from Definition 2.1.

Corollary 2.5. Let G be an $I\beta TG$, $r, s \in G$, and $A \subseteq G$. Then the β -openness (β -closeness) of one of the sets $A, -A, r + A, A + r$, and $r + A + s$ follows the others.

PROOF. The proof follows from Theorem 2.4.

Corollary 2.6. If G is an $I\beta TG$, A is a β -open subset and B is an arbitrary subset of G , then $A + B$ and $B + A$ are β -open sets.

PROOF. The proof follows from Corollary 2.5.

Proposition 2.7. Let G be an $I\beta TG$ and let B and C be subsets of G . Then the following statements are true:

1. $\beta Cl(B) + \beta Cl(C) \subseteq \beta Cl(B + C)$;
2. $\beta Cl(-C) = -\beta Cl(C)$;
3. $\beta Cl(B) - \beta Cl(C) \subseteq \beta Cl(B - C)$;
4. $\beta Cl(r + B + r) = r + \beta Cl(B) + r$ where $r \in G$.

- PROOF. 1. Let $x \in \beta Cl(B) + \beta Cl(C)$ and Q be any β -open set of x . Consider $x = b + c$ where $b \in \beta Cl(B)$ and $c \in \beta Cl(C)$, then there exist β -open sets H and K of b and c respectively such that $H + K \subseteq Q$. From the fact that $B \cap H \neq \emptyset$ and $C \cap K \neq \emptyset$, there exist $b_1 \in B \cap H$ and $c_1 \in C \cap K$. This implies that $b_1 + c_1 \in (B + C) \cap Q \neq \emptyset$ and the result follows.
2. The proof follows from Lemma 1.1 and Theorem 2.4.
 3. It follows from part 1 and part 2.
 4. We set $h_r(x) = R_r \circ L_r(x) = r + x + r$ which is a homeomorphism and the rest follows from Lemma 1.1.

Proposition 2.8. If G is an $I\beta TG$, then the following statements are true:

1. If C is a subgroup of G , so is $\beta Cl(C)$;
2. If C is a normal subgroup of G , so is $\beta Cl(C)$;

- PROOF. 1. Since C is a subgroup of G , then $C - C \subseteq C$. This implies that $\beta Cl(C - C) \subseteq \beta Cl(C)$. By Proposition 2.7, part 3., we have $\beta Cl(C) - \beta Cl(C) \subseteq \beta Cl(C)$. Hence $\beta Cl(C)$ is subgroup of G .
2. Since C is a normal subgroup of G , then $-r + C + r = C$ for all $r \in G$. From this we have $\beta Cl(-r + C + r) = \beta Cl(C)$. By Proposition 2.7, part 4., we obtain $\beta -r + Cl(C) + r = \beta Cl(C)$. Thus $\beta Cl(C)$ is normal subgroup of G .

Definition 2.9. A topological space X is called irresolute β -homogeneous if for each pair of points $a, b \in X$ there exists an irresolute β -homeomorphism $\alpha: X \rightarrow X$ such that $\alpha(a) = b$.

Lemma 2.10. Every $I\beta TG$ is irresolute β -homogeneous.

PROOF. Let G be an $I\beta TG$ and $a, b \in G$. By Theorem 2.4 we have the homeomorphism $L_r(x) = r + x$. Set $r = b - a$ and the result follows.

3. Irresolute β -topological rings

In this section, we define and study irresolute β -topological rings ($I\beta TR$) with some examples.

Definition 3.1. A topology τ on a ring R is an irresolute β -topological ring if the following conditions hold:

1. (R, τ) is $I\beta TG$.
2. the mapping $g: R \times R \rightarrow R, g(x, y) = xy$ is irresolute β -continuous.

Theorem 3.2. If R is an $I\beta TR$, then

1. For every element $r \in R$, the mappings $\psi_r: R \rightarrow R, \psi_r(x) = xr, \phi_r: R \rightarrow R, \phi_r(x) = rx$ are irresolute β -continuous of the space R . If r is a unit, then they are irresolute β -homeomorphisms.
2. The mapping $h: R \times R \rightarrow R, h(x, y) = yx$ is an irresolute β -continuous.

PROOF. The proof follows from Definition 3.1.

Corollary 3.3. If R is an $I\beta TR$ and $r \in R$, then

1. the subset A is β -open (closed) set if and only if rA is β -open (closed) set.
2. the subset A is β -open (closed) set if and only if Ar is β -open (closed) set.
3. the subset A is β -open (closed) set if and only if rAr is β -open (closed) set.

PROOF. The proof follows from Theorem 3.2.

Proposition 3.4. Let R be an $I\beta TR$ and let B and C be subsets of R . Then the following statements are true:

1. $\beta Cl(B), \beta Cl(C) \subseteq \beta Cl(B.C)$;

2. $\beta Cl(rCr^{-1}) = r\beta Cl(C)r^{-1}$ where r is a unit in R .
3. $\beta Cl(B).C \subseteq \beta Cl(B.C)$;
4. $B.\beta Cl(C) \subseteq \beta Cl(B.C)$;

PROOF. The proof follows from Lemma 1.1 and Theorem 3.2.

Proposition 3.5. If R is an $I\beta TR$, then the following statements are true:

1. If C is a subring of R , then is $\beta Cl(C)$ is a subring of R ;
2. If C is an ideal of R , then $\beta Cl(C)$ is an ideal of R ;

PROOF. 1. By Proposition 2.7. C is a subgroup of R . Since C is a subring of R , then $CC \subseteq C$. By Proposition 3.4, the result follows.

2. By Proposition 2.7. C is a subgroup of R . Since C is an ideal of R , then $RC \subseteq C$. By Proposition 3.4, the result follows.

Theorem 3.6. Let R be an $I\beta TR$, and A be an ideal of a β -dense subring B of R . Then $\beta Cl(A)$ is an ideal of R .

PROOF. From Proposition 3.4 and being B a β -dense, we have $\beta Cl(A).R = \beta Cl(A).\beta Cl(B) \subseteq \beta Cl(A.B) \subseteq \beta Cl(A)$. Similarly, $\beta Cl(A)$ is a left ideal of R .

Proposition 3.7. Let R be an $I\beta TR$. If A and B are two ideals of R , then $\beta Cl(\beta Cl(A.B)) = \beta Cl(A.B)$.

PROOF. It is clear.

Proposition 3.8. Every subring of an $I\beta TR$ is an $I\beta TR$.

PROOF. It is clear.

Theorem 3.9. Let R be an irresolute β -Hausdorff ring and S be a subring of R .

1. If S is commutative, so is $\beta Cl(S)$.
2. A multiplicative identity of S is a multiplicative identity of $\beta Cl(S)$.
3. The center $Z(R)$ of R is β -closed.

PROOF. Since R is β -Hausdorff space, irresolute β -continuous on R agrees on β -closed subsets of R .

1. Since $(x, y) \rightarrow xy$ is an irresolute β -continuous from $R \times R$ to R by part 2 of Theorem 3.2, it agrees with $(x, y) \rightarrow yx$ on β -closed subsets of $R \times R$ containing $\beta Cl(S) \times \beta Cl(S)$. Hence $\beta Cl(S)$ is commutative.
2. Assume that S has a multiplicative identity 1. Since the irresolute β -continuous functions $f(x) = x.1$, $h(x) = 1.x$ and the identity function agree on β -closed subsets of R containing S , they agree on $\beta Cl(S)$. Therefore 1 is the identity of $\beta Cl(S)$.
3. The functions mentioned in part 1 agree on β -closed subsets of $R \times R$ containing $R \times Z(R)$, they agree on their β -closure in $R \times \beta Cl(Z(R))$. Hence $\beta Cl(Z(R)) \subseteq Z(R)$. So $Z(R)$ is β -closed.

4. Irresolute β -Topological R -modules

Definition 4.1. Let R be an $I\beta TR$, M be an R -module. A topology τ on M is an $I\beta TM$ if the following conditions hold:

1. (M, τ) is an $I\beta TG$.
2. the mapping $h: R \times M \rightarrow M, h(\lambda, x) = \lambda x$ is an irresolute β -continuous.

Theorem 4.2. Let R be an $I\beta TR$, M be an $I\beta TM$, Q a subset in R and B a subset in M . Then

1. For $r \in R$, the mapping $\psi_r: M \rightarrow M, \psi_r(x) = rx$ is an irresolute β -continuous.
2. For $a \in M$ the mapping $\psi_a: R \rightarrow M, \psi_a(x) = xa$ is an irresolute β -continuous.
3. $\beta Cl(Q)_R \cdot \beta Cl(B)_M \subseteq \beta Cl(Q \cdot B)_M$.

PROOF. The proof of the first and second part follow from Definition 4.1. The proof of the last part follows from 2 and Lemma 1.1.

Theorem 4.3. Let R be an $I\beta TR$ and M be an $I\beta TM$. Let Q be a subset of R and N be a subset of M . Then

1. If N is a Q -stable subset, then $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is a $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ stable subset.
2. If Q is a subring of R and N is a Q -submodule of M , then $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ is a subring of R .
3. If N is a Q -submodule, then $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is a $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ -submodule.

PROOF. 1. Since N is a Q -stable subset, then $N \cdot Q \subseteq N$, this implies that $\beta Cl(Q)_R \cdot \beta Cl(N)_M \subseteq \beta Cl(Q \cdot N)_M \subseteq \beta Cl(N)_M$ by Theorem 4.2. Thus $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is a $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ stable subset.
 2. By Proposition 2.8, $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ and $\beta Cl(N)_M$ are subgroups of R and M correspondingly. Since Q is a Q -stable subset of the irresolute β -topological R -module R and N is a Q -stable subset of the irresolute β -topological R -module M . By part 1, $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ is a $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ -stable subset of the irresolute β -topological R -module R . That is $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ is a subring of R .
 3. By part 1. $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is a $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ stable subset. Since $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ is a subring of R , then $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is a $\beta Cl(Q)_R$ -submodule.

Corollary 4.4. Let Q be a dense subring of an irresolute β -topological R -module R and N be a Q -submodule of an irresolute β -topological R -module M . Then $\beta Cl(N)_M$ is a submodule of irresolute β -topological R -module M . In particular, the closure of any submodule of an irresolute β -topological R -module is also an irresolute β -topological R -module.

PROOF. The proof follows from Theorem 4.3.

Corollary 4.5. Let Q be a dense left (right, two-sided) ideal of an $I\beta TR$ R and P be a dense left (right, two-sided) ideal of the ring Q . Then $\beta Cl(P)_Q$ is left (right, two-sided) ideal of the ring R .

PROOF. Since $\beta Cl(P)_Q = \beta Cl(P)_R \cap Q$, then $\beta Cl(P)_Q$ is an intersection of two left (right, two-sided) ideals of Q and $\beta Cl(P)_R$ of the ring R , hence, is a left (right, two-sided) indeed, too.

Remark 4.6. Let Q be a subring of a topological ring R and N be a submodule of an irresolute β -topological R -module M . Let Q_0 and R_0 be the smallest β -closed ideals of the irresolute β -topological rings Q and R correspondingly, N_0 and M_0 be the smallest β -closed submodules of the irresolute β -topological R -modules N and M correspondingly. Then $Q_0 = R_0 \cap Q$ and $N_0 = M_0 \cap N$.

Corollary 4.7. Let Q be a dense subring of an irresolute β -topological ring R and I be a left (right, two-sided) ideal of the ring Q . Then $\beta(I)_R$ is a left (right, two-sided) ideal of the ring R .

PROOF. The proof follows from Theorem 4.3.

Definition 4.8. An irresolute β -topological ring R (an irresolute β -topological R -module M is called topologically simple if the ring R (R -module M) has no β -closed ideals (β -closed submodules) different from R_0 and R (from M_0 and M).

Proposition 4.9. Any dense subring of an irresolute β -topologically simple is an irresolute β -topologically simple. A dense submodule of an irresolute β -topologically simple is an irresolute β -topologically simple.

PROOF. Let Q be a dense subring of an irresolute β -topological ring R , and let Q_0 and R_0 be the smallest β -closed ideals of the rings Q and R correspondingly. Let P be a β -closed ideal of Q , then, due to Corollary 4.7, $\beta Cl(P)_R$ is a β -closed ideal of R , and since the ring R is irresolute β -topologically simple, then either $\beta Cl(P)_R = R_0$, or $\beta Cl(P)_R = R$. Since $P = \beta Cl(P)_Q = \beta Cl(P)_R \cap Q$, then either $P = R_0 \cap Q = Q_0$, or $P = R \cap Q = Q$, that is, Q is an irresolute β -topologically simple ring. The proof of the second part of the proposition is similarly.

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References

- [1] El-Deeb S. N. Abd El-Monsef M. E. and Mahmoud R. A., *β -open sets and β -continuous mappings*, Bull. Fac. Sci. Assint Univ (1983), no. 12, 77–90.
- [2] Mohammed Salih H.M., *On irresolute topological rings*, Journal of Advanced Studies in Topology **9** (2018), no. 2, 130–134.
- [3] Billawria S. and Sharma Sh., *On beta-topological rings*, Journal of algebra and related topics **9** (2021), no. 1, 51–60.